

Kinetic study of solvent effects on the hydrolysis of di-2-chloroaniline phosphate in dioxane and dimethyl sulfoxide-water medium

Nitin Choure and S. A. Bhoite*

School of Studies in Chemistry, Pt. Ravishankar Shukla University, Raipur-492 010, Chhattisgarh, India

E-mail : sa.bhoite10@gmail.com, nitin.choure1@gmail.com

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Abstract : Kinetic study of di-2-chloroaniline phosphate was carried out in dioxane and dimethyl sulfoxide-water mixtures of varying compositions 20–50% (v/v). The rate of reaction increases with increasing proportion of dioxane and dimethyl sulfoxide at 80 and 90 °C. The activation parameters (E_a , ΔH^\ddagger , ΔG^\ddagger , $-\Delta S^\ddagger$) have been evaluated and variations of these parameters have been explained on the basis of solvent-solute interaction, solvent of the transition state of the medium.

Keywords : Kinetics, hydrolysis, solvent effects, di-2-chloroaniline phosphate.

Introduction

Phosphate ester hydrolysis plays a very important role in energy metabolism and in various cellular signal transduction pathways in biological system¹. Phosphate mono- and di-esters are relatively stable and play a central role in biochemical reaction². Phosphate monoesters are intermediates in a variety of metabolic pathways and phosphate di-esters are the essential components of DNA and RNA³.

Solvent effect plays an important role in determining chemical reactivity. The rate of an elementary chemical reaction may change by order of magnitude when the solvent is changed⁴. Kinetic solvent effect on chemical reactions in different media are usually correlated in term of “solvent polarity”, which sum up all the specific and non-specific interactions of the media with initial and transition state.

Experimental

Di-2-chloroaniline phosphate was synthesized by literature method⁵. It involves the reaction of 2-chloroaniline and phosphorous oxychloride in (2 : 1) mole ratio to give crude di-ester as a solid. The crude product so obtained was recrystallized by ammonia and hydrochloric acid to get pure sample. The melting point of di-ester is 197 °C. All the chemicals used were of A.R. grade and all solutions were prepared in triply distilled water.

Hydrolysis of di-2-chloroaniline phosphate ester was

carried by employing 5.0×10^{-4} mol dm⁻³ solution in dioxane-water and dimethyl sulfoxide-water binary systems at various composition (20 to 50%, v/v) of dioxane and dimethyl sulfoxide at 80 and 90 °C. The progress of the kinetic study was carried out by Allen’s modified method⁶ using spectrophotometer at 735 nm. Pseudo-first order rate constant k_e were derived from first order rate equation.

Allen’s modified method involves the measurement of inorganic phosphate formed from the ester, during the course of its hydrolysis. Phosphomolybdate complex $[(NH_4)_3PO_4 \cdot 12MoO_3]$ is formed by the inorganic phosphate with ammonium molybdate. This complex is reduced to molybdenum blue, a soluble complex, by addition of 2,4-diaminophenol dihydrochloride solution. The blue colour so generated is fully developed within 10 min. The intensity of the blue colour is directly proportional to the amount of the free phosphoric acid. The optical density of the blue colour developed followed Beer’s law.

Results and discussion

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The kinetics of the hydrolysis of di-2-chloroaniline phosphate ester (1) was studied in pH 4.17 at 80 and 90 °C. The diphosphate esters are not soluble in water, a 20/80 (v/v) dioxane-water and dimethyl sulfoxide-water medium was used. It was found that the rate constant increases with increase in percentage of dioxane and dimethyl sulfoxide from 20 to 50% (v/v) in binary aqueous mixtures at both temperatures. The pH is kept constant at 4.17 using phosphate buffer. The hydrolysis reactions were carried out at the same buffer. Pseudo-first order rate constants have been obtained which are summarized in Table 1.

constants of the reaction media go on increasing with gradual addition of solvent. Here our findings are fully in accordance with the qualitative prediction of Hughes and Ingold.

The solvents dioxane and dimethyl sulfoxide exerted greater accelerating effect on rate. Intermolecular association of this solvent occurs in such type of binary mixtures. The possible factors influencing the rate are solute-solvent interaction and the solvation changes of reactant and transition state. Higher rates are obtained in dimethyl sulfoxide and the lower rates are found in dioxane because dimethyl sulfoxide have high polarity than diox-

Table 1. Kinetic rate data for the hydrolysis of di-2-chloroaniline phosphate ester at different temperatures and solvent mixtures [Substrate] = 5.0×10^{-4} M/dm³

	Dioxane (% v/v)					DMSO (% v/v)			
	80 °C	log <i>k</i>	90 °C	log <i>k</i>		80 °C	log <i>k</i>	90 °C	log <i>k</i>
20	3.43	0.53	6.96	0.84	20	4.67	0.67	9.84	0.99
30	3.92	0.59	7.94	0.90	30	5.35	0.73	11.05	1.04
40	4.65	0.67	9.20	0.96	40	6.47	0.81	13.08	1.12
50	5.74	0.76	11.42	1.06	50	7.48	0.87	14.92	1.17

Table 1 shows that the rate constant values are gradually increasing with the gradual addition of dioxane and dimethyl sulfoxide (DMSO). Dioxane is regarded as polar aprotic solvent while dimethyl sulfoxide is regarded as dipolar aprotic solvent. The effect of solvents on rate of hydrolysis indicates the transition state in which charge is dispersed⁷. The increasing trend in the values of rate constants needs to be discussed in the light of Hughes and Ingold⁸ predictions according to which an increase in the dielectric constant values of the reaction media causes an increase in the rate when there is concentration or construction of charges on the transition state and causes a decrease in the rate when there is diffusion or destruction of charges in the transition state. The values of dielectric

ane. Parker and Tomilison pointed out the breakdown of water-water interaction by adding dimethyl sulfoxide, as a co-solvent in it⁹. This solvent-sheath breaking nature of dimethyl sulfoxide has differential effect on solvent of initial state and of transition state. The rate constants will naturally be affected by such specific solvation changes. As dimethyl sulfoxide is a poor anion solvater there will be decreased in solvation sheath of the anion, OH⁻ (reactant) with gradual increase in dimethyl sulfoxide proportion in the reaction medium.

The activation parameters ΔH^\ddagger , ΔG^\ddagger , $-\Delta S^\ddagger$, exhibit non linear variation with solvent composition for mixed-solvent systems. Table 2 shows that the values of the entropy of activation ΔS^\ddagger are negative in all solvent

Table 2. Activation parameters for the hydrolysis of di-2-chloroaniline phosphate ester

	Dioxane (% v/v)					DMSO (% v/v)			
	<i>E_a</i>	ΔH^\ddagger	ΔG^\ddagger	$-\Delta S^\ddagger$		<i>E_a</i>	ΔH^\ddagger	ΔG^\ddagger	$-\Delta S^\ddagger$
20	76.05	73.12	103.65	86.50	78.51	75.57	102.80	77.12	
30	73.60	70.67	103.31	92.49	76.05	73.12	102.41	82.86	
40	71.15	68.22	102.74	97.79	73.60	70.67	101.81	88.22	
50	73.60	70.67	102.15	89.18	71.15	68.22	102.20	93.96	

E_a, ΔH^\ddagger , ΔG^\ddagger , in kJmol⁻¹ and ΔS^\ddagger , in JK⁻¹ mol⁻¹.

Note

mixtures investigated. This indicates that in all of these solvent mixtures the polar transition state is preferentially solvated by water molecules. The ΔG^\ddagger value decreases with composition of dioxane and dimethyl sulfoxide-water mixtures.

Conclusions :

The rate of reaction increases with increase in percentage of dioxane and dimethyl sulfoxide mixtures at different temperatures at constant pH 4.17. This is attributed to differential solvation of the transition state, solute-solvent interactions of the medium. The activation parameters ΔH^\ddagger , ΔG^\ddagger , $-\Delta S^\ddagger$ exhibit non linear variation with solvent composition for mixed-solvent systems.

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